

Figure 1: Stakeholder Workshop in Vienna, CC BY Helena Bernhardt

Report on workshops and conferences in the partner cities

Open Urban Sustainability Hubs (OPUSH) project |
ERA-Net Urban Transformation Capacities (ENUTC)

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Summary

This report highlights the project's capacity building and dissemination activities, which were key to embedding Citizen science within institutional, national, and international contexts. Through workshops, trainings, research talks, and conferences, the consortium strengthened internal collaboration and expanded its outreach to academic, policy, and community audiences. Local Citizen Science experiments showcased inclusive, co-created research in action, while ongoing institutional dialogue ensured lasting impact. These combined efforts established a solid foundation for continued innovation and systemic change in Citizen Science across Europe.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

AESOP	Association for European Schools of Planning
CSO	Civil society organisation
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
GLAM	Galleries, libraries, archives and museums
LIBER	Association of European Research Libraries
OPUSH	Open Urban Sustainability Hubs

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1. Introduction

Definition of events included in the report: workshops, conferences, trainings on-site or virtual, research talks, definition capacity building vs. dissemination activity.

This report presents a structured overview of the project's capacity building and dissemination efforts, which were essential to strengthening institutional expertise, fostering collaboration, and expanding the impact of Citizen Science initiatives at local, national, and international levels.

Definitions & Scope:

Activities covered include workshops, training sessions (virtual and in-person), research talks, working group participation, and academic conferences. Capacity building refers to internal development within the consortium and partners, while dissemination focuses on outreach and knowledge transfer to broader audiences.

Consortium Capacity Building:

Four major project team meetings were held in Vienna, Tallinn, and Delft, aligning internal teams around core work packages and fostering exchange across institutions. These meetings served as foundational touchpoints for coordination and strategic planning.

International Engagement:

Project members actively contributed to major conferences such as LIBER, AESOP, ECSA, and Living Knowledge, reaching global research and practitioner communities. Participation in working groups and Erasmus+ staff mobility initiatives deepened engagement with emerging practices in Citizen Science, library innovation, and sustainability.

National & Regional Events:

Each core city—Barcelona, Delft, Tallinn, and Vienna—hosted a range of events tailored to national audiences. Highlights include the Austrian Citizen Science Conference, city-level stakeholder dialogues, and integration into national research and library networks.

Local Implementation & Citizen Science Experiments:

Hands-on experiments were carried out in each partner city, involving residents in co-created research on urban issues such as heat mapping, energy transition, and public space usage. These experiments exemplified the practical integration of Citizen Science into community life, emphasizing inclusivity and real-world impact.

Ongoing Institutional Dialogue:

Regular research talks and internal workshops—such as TU Wien's strategy sessions and local library dialogues—ensured the continuous embedding of Citizen Science within institutional frameworks and decision-making processes.

2. Capacity building events within the consortium

Figure 2: Kick-Off Meeting in Vienna, CC BY TU Wien

- Kick-off meeting with international project team (Vienna, October 2022)
- Project team meeting focussing on WP4 (Tallinn, September 2023)
- Project team meeting focussing on WP5 (Vienna, April 2024)
- Final project team meeting (Barcelona, March 2025)

3. International capacity building events

Figure 3: LIBER 2024 Conference in Limassol, CC BY 2.0 LIBER Europe

International Conferences

LIBER Conference (Budapest, July 2023)

- Peer, C., *Research Libraries in Open Urban Sustainability Hubs*

AESOP Conference (Lodz, July 2023)

- Dembski, F., Sarv, L., Ilves, L., Guba, B. et al. *Urban hubs, participation, citizen science and digital tools. Pathways to more sustainable and democratic urban quarters*
- Peer, C. *Social innovative settlement processes for large urban development areas in the making*

COESO Conference 2023 (Paris, Oktober 2023)

- Harnacker, S., et al. *Learning participatory research: creating common spaces for training and mutual learning*
- Harnacker, S., et al. *Working with vulnerable groups in innovation policy processes and citizen science formats*

ECSCA Conference (Vienna, April 2024)

- Bernhardt, H., Bonhoure, I., Peer, C., Harnacker, S., Perelló, J. *Urban Heat Stories: a chatbot for micro-stories on urban heat in Vienna*
- Harnacker, S., et al. *Citizen science in higher education: exploring the opportunities, challenges and synergies*
- Perelló, J., Bonhoure, I., Breiding, R. *Sharing the experience of different citizen science training programs: main outcomes and remaining challenges*

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ECSCA Citizen Science Day, (Vienna, April 2024)

- Bernhardt, H., Peer, C., Harnacker, S., *Urban Heat Stories*
- Panigyrakis, P. *Check je Plek*

LIBER Conference (Limassol, July 2024)

- Harnacker, S., et al. *Breaking Boundaries: Advocacy for Citizen Science in European Higher Education Libraries*
- Harnacker, S., Panigyrakis, P. *Connecting Cities and Universities: Libraries' role in Citizen Science Pilots of Urban Sustainability*

Living Knowledge Conference (Girona, Spain, July 2024)

- Bonhoure, I. *Citizen Science = Data Science?*
- Breiding, R., Perelló, J., Bonhoure, I. *Citizen Science Collaborative, fostering social inclusion in SENSE.STEAM education*

ANL Conference (Nürnberg, October 2024)

- Dembski, F., *Digitale Zwillinge und naturbasierte Lösungen (Keynote)*

CeOS-SE Conference (Zagreb, October 2024)

- Harnacker, S. *Libraries as knowledge hubs: Empowering neighborhoods with Citizen Science*

Smart City Conference (Barcelona, November 2024)

“Biržiška Readings '24: Culture and Citizen Science” (Panevėžys, Lithuania, December 2024)

- Bonhoure, I., *Libraries as Open Knowledge Hubs: How Citizen Science Can Play a Role.*

International Working Group Participation

Figure 4: Best Poster Award (LIBER 2024 Conference), TUW_lib with the LIBER CS Working Group, CC BY 2.0 LIBER Europe

CESAER Subgroup Citizen Science (Beate Guba)

ECSA Citizen Science and universities Working Group (Sebastian Harnacker)

LIBER Citizen Science Working Group (Sebastian Harnacker)

ECS Network of Researchers for Citizen Science- #NR4CS (Sebastian Harnacker)

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3.4 International capacity building events

Figure 5: Erasmus+ Staff Mobility at SDU Library, CC BY SDU

Erasmus+ Staff mobility : « NEW ROLES FOR LIBRARIES: Sustainability & Citizen Science » (The University of Southern Denmark, June 2024, Sebastian Harnacker)

LIBER CS Working Group : Citizen Science: Partnerships for Science and Society (Limassol, Cyprus, Sebastian Harnacker)

ECLAC - LIBER Citizen Science Masterclass (online, November 2024, Sebastian Harnacker)

Erasmus+ Staff mobility : « Scientific workshop by Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech) at Avalinn Hub, Tallinn funded by TU Delft Erasmus staff mobility grant. *Digital skills, engaged citizens: More sustainable and democratic cities.*»

“Biržiška Readings '24: Culture and Citizen Science”, Citizen Science Training for Young Librarians (Panevėžys, Lithuania, December 2024, Isabelle Bonhoure)

Smart City EXPO. Workshop: Heat Chronicles, citizen science to better understand urban heat. Opensystems UB: Josep Perelló, Isabelle Bonhoure, Maday Rivero. Public Library Josep Janés: Raquel Segura.

EULiST Symposium Climate-neutral and climate-resilient cities and universities in Europe (Leibniz University Hannover, December 2024, Sebastian Harnacker)

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4. National capacity building events

Figure 6: Workshop with the City of Tallinn, CC BY TalTech

Barcelona

UB Citizen Science Training: "Training in Citizen Science: introduction and deepening in the development of participatory research projects with social commitment", November 2023

Delft

Mid-term and Kick-off Event for ENUTC and BTC calls & Agora Dialogue (Delft and Utrecht November 2023, Phoebus Panigyrakis, Frank van der Hoeven, Christian Peers (online))

Tallinn

Virtual Reality Workshop together with the City of Tallinn (September 2022)

Vienna

- Austrian Citizen Science Conference (Linz, April 2023)
- 2nd Austrian Libraries Congress (Vienna, March 2025)

5. Local and regional capacity building events

Figure 7: Delft Makers Faire, CC BY Phoebus Panigyraakis

Barcelona

- The socio-territorial perspective of the ecological transition and the climate emergency, organized by the Taula del Tercer Sector (Barcelona, October 2024)
- A Neighborhood Perspective on Heat in the Metropolitan Area of Barcelona through Heat Chronicles project (Barcelona, November 2024)
- Citizen Science, Libraries and Open Knowledge (Barcelona, December 2024)

Delft

- Makers Faire Festival Report, (Delft, 13-14 May 2023)
- OSCD+4TU.Research.Data networking event (Delft, September 2023)
- Denk mee over DOK, Open day of the public library of Delft with public discussions and presentations (Delft, June 2023)

Tallinn

- Presentation of Citizen Science Experiments and "Aviko" Hub concept at Bayerische Akademie für Naturschutz und Landschaftspflege (Nürnberg, October 2024)

Vienna

- Kick-off with national project partners (2022)
- 1st stakeholder workshop with public libraries of Vienna and Science Center Netzwerk - Society for Science Communication (Oktober 2023)
- Tuesday Lounge « Citizen Science and Sustainability Transformation at TU Wien » (January 2024)
- Stakeholder workshop with museums and city administration « Citizen Science in der nachhaltigen Stadtentwicklung » (February 2024)

6. Local Citizen Science experiments

Figure 8: Local CS experiment in Barcelona, CC BY Isabelle Bonhoure

Barcelona

Urban Heat Stories Pilot :

- Summer 2023 : total of 9 Citizen Science sessions in 3 locations.
- Summer 2024 : total of 30 Citizen Science sessions in 5 locations.

Delft

Check je plek :

- Research design session, Melarium Nature Centre, Natuurlijk Delfland, 31 January 2024.
- Research design session with University of Utrecht researchers, 06 November 2023,
- Research design session with OPEN/DOK library personnel, 24 February 2024
- Workshop session, at OPEN/DOK library, 3 June 2024.
- Co-design and presentation session, 5th November 2024,
- Research design session with Blok 74.

Energy Transition :

- Energy Coaches workshop, 7 July 2023.
- Research design session with 015 Duurzaamheid, 10 October 2023
- Meeting with Data Steward – 19 October 2023
- Meeting with Privacy Team 13 March 2024
- Interview sessions, 30 Sept.-4 October 2024.

Tallinn

AViKo Pilot: collaborative Virtual Reality, Avalinn City Hub (June 2023)

Niine Street Pilot: CS Workshop at Kalamaja Museum (September 2023)

Vienna

Gumpendorfer Straße Pilot:

- Meetings with local partners (PlanSinn, Carla Lo)
- Meetings with teachers (Amerlinggymnasium, WMS Loquaipplatz)
- Workshops with students (Amerlinggymnasium, WMS Loquaipplatz)

Urban Heat Stories Pilot:

- 1st stakeholder workshop for « Urban Heat Stories » experiment (June 2023)
- Workshops with senior citizens (September 2023)
- Presentation of results at European Researchers' Night (September 2023)
- Presentation of results and collecting feedback at Bezirkssenioreninnentag – Senior Citizens Day (October 2023)
- 2nd stakeholder workshop for « Urban Heat Stories » experiment (March 2024)
- Workshops with school children (May-June 2024)
- Participation at Austrian Young-Science-Congress (October 2024)

7. Conclusion

The project's capacity building and dissemination activities have played a pivotal role in embedding Citizen Science within institutional, national, and international frameworks. Through a diverse range of events including workshops, trainings, research talks, and conferences the consortium not only strengthened internal collaboration and expertise but also extended its reach to broader academic, policy, and community audiences. The integration of Citizen Science experiments in partner cities demonstrated the practical and inclusive potential of co-created research, while sustained institutional dialogue ensured long-term impact. Together, these efforts have laid a strong foundation for continued innovation, knowledge sharing, and systemic change in Citizen Science practice across Europe.

